

EFFECTIVENESS OF CLINICAL APPROACHES IN THE TREATMENT OF GONARTHROSIS IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS

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Gonarthrosis is a widespread, socially significant, multifactorial disease of large joints, characterized by inflammatory and degenerative changes in skeletal connective tissues, leading to disability in the working-age population.

According to data provided by the WHO, the disability and mortality rates associated with OA vary by gender, reaching 65% in postmenopausal women and no more than 30% in men.

Deforming arthrosis of the knee joint, or gonarthrosis, is one of the most common diseases of the musculoskeletal system. It tends to progress with age, becoming more severe and difficult to treat compared to other locomotor disorders (Tkacheva O.N. et al., 2021; Raimagambetov E.K. et al., 2023). Moreover, this disease in elderly (61–74 years) and senile (75–89 years) patients is often complicated and, in many cases, ends with surgical intervention (Ilnitsky A.N. et al., 2019; Filimonova O.G., Leushina E.A., 2021).

In recent years, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has been widely used, allowing the detection of pathological changes in the articular cartilage matrix at early stages, as well as visualization of meniscal and ligamentous lesions of the knee joint (Lila A.M. et al., 2023). Based on these considerations, early diagnosis of this pathological condition, identifying its clinical course in elderly and senile patients, determining prognosis, and improving treatment strategies are of great importance.

Research Objective: To determine and evaluate the effectiveness of conservative and surgical treatment methods by characterizing the clinical status of elderly and senile patients diagnosed with gonarthrosis.

Materials and Methods: Clinical studies were conducted at the “*Star Orthomed*” private clinic and the Bukhara State Medical Institute from 2022 to 2025. A total of 158 patients aged 56 to 80 years were examined, including 25 men (15.82±2.90%) and 133 women (84.18±2.90%). The majority were rural residents (74.68±3.46%, n=118), while urban residents accounted for 25.32±3.46% (n=40). Thus, the prevalence of gonarthrosis was 4.06 times higher in women than in men, consistent with data from other scientific sources. The

predominance of rural patients (2.95 times more than urban) may be explained by their higher physical workload and limited access to healthcare. Most patients were retired ($98.10 \pm 1.09\%$, $n=155$), with only 2 working individuals ($1.27 \pm 0.89\%$) and 1 farmer ($0.63 \pm 0.63\%$).

The age distribution was as follows: 56–59 years — 27 patients ($17.09 \pm 2.99\%$), 60–74 years — 95 patients ($60.13 \pm 3.90\%$), and 75–89 years — 36 patients ($22.78 \pm 3.30\%$).

Since the study involved elderly and senile individuals, comorbidities were of particular importance as they could influence the course and outcome of gonarthrosis. Comorbid diseases were absent in $33.54 \pm 3.76\%$ of patients, while $66.46 \pm 3.76\%$ ($n=105$) had one or more. In total, 228 comorbidities were identified, averaging 2.17 per patient. The most common were hypertension ($44.94 \pm 3.96\%$), arterial hypertension ($44.30 \pm 3.96\%$), ischemic heart disease ($20.25 \pm 3.20\%$), and obesity ($17.72 \pm 3.04\%$).

Patients were selected randomly, ensuring randomized research conditions. Statistical analysis was performed using variation statistics methods with Microsoft Excel software.

Results and Discussion: Both conservative and surgical treatment methods were applied depending on disease stage and clinical symptoms. Conservative treatment was performed in early stages (Kosin'skaya I–II, Kellgren–Lawrence I–II), while surgery was used in later stages (Kosin'skaya II–III, Kellgren–Lawrence III–IV).

The main goals of conservative therapy were to reduce pain, stabilize degenerative-dystrophic processes in the knee joint, achieve clinical compensation, preserve range of motion, and relieve synovitis symptoms. An individualized approach was applied for each patient, considering age, comorbidities, and contraindications to invasive procedures. Conservative treatment included both pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods.

To reduce mechanical stress on the knee, patients were advised to avoid jogging, prolonged walking, squatting, climbing stairs, heavy physical labor, and high-impact exercises. Instead, therapeutic exercise (physical therapy) was prescribed to strengthen thigh and calf muscles, improve knee function, and reduce pain.

Since no specific etiopathogenetic drug therapy for gonarthrosis exists, pharmacological treatment was symptomatic and personalized. The most frequently used drugs were **NaCl + Lysine** and **B-vitamin complex** ($76.92 \pm 3.90\%$ and $76.07 \pm 3.94\%$, respectively). Other commonly used drugs

included **NaCl + Trental** ($63.25 \pm 4.46\%$), **Keiver** ($62.39 \pm 4.48\%$), and **Suvitol** ($56.41 \pm 4.86\%$), known for their pathogenetic and symptomatic effects.

Among non-drug treatments, **physiotherapy** was the most widely applied and recommended as part of the main therapeutic protocol. Physiotherapy was used in $94.87 \pm 2.04\%$ of conservatively treated patients ($n=111$). The most common modalities were **ultrasound therapy** ($93.16 \pm 2.33\%$, $n=109$), **magnetotherapy** ($90.60 \pm 2.70\%$, $n=106$), and **electrophoresis** ($89.74 \pm 2.80\%$, $n=105$).

These methods effectively reduced inflammation, improved circulation, accelerated tissue regeneration, and enhanced the effects of medications.

In the advanced stages of gonarthrosis, surgical intervention was performed in 41 patients ($25.95 \pm 3.49\%$). The most frequent procedures included **diagnostic arthroscopy** ($58.54 \pm 7.69\%$), **medial meniscectomy** ($53.66 \pm 7.79\%$), and **total knee arthroplasty** ($39.02 \pm 7.62\%$). The lower frequency of surgeries compared to conservative treatments (2.85 times less) reflects a preference for less invasive management unless surgical intervention was absolutely necessary.

All surgical outcomes were successful, resulting in pain reduction and improved joint function. In total knee replacement cases ($n=16$), all prostheses were well tolerated without complications. Postoperative monitoring confirmed good healing, absence of infection, and faster recovery.

Conclusions: In elderly and senile patients with gonarthrosis, due to changes in pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics, the presence of comorbidities, and the risk of polypharmacy, non-drug treatment methods were prioritized over pharmacological therapy. An individualized treatment approach was implemented, considering each patient's general condition, disease duration, and previous treatment response. Among physiotherapeutic methods, **ultrasound (93.16%)**, **magnetotherapy (90.60%)**, and **electrophoresis (89.74%)** proved to be the most effective.

In advanced stages, when conservative treatment was ineffective, **surgical interventions** were performed (total of 94 operations), with diagnostic arthroscopy, medial meniscectomy, and total arthroplasty being the most common. All surgical outcomes were satisfactory, demonstrating significant pain reduction and improvement in knee joint mobility and function.

